

ISOLATION OF PURE POTASSIUM NITRITE FROM THE COMMERCIAL SUBSTANCE

By TRAMBAKAL MOHANLAL OZA AND BHASKAR RAMAKRISHNA WALAVALKAR.

Fairly appreciable quantities of pure potassium nitrite have been isolated from the Merck's pure potassium nitrite containing about 92% of the substance. When a concentrated aqueous solution of the substance is cooled in a freezing mixture of ice and ammonium chloride pure nitrite or mixtures of nitrite and nitrate richer in nitrite than the original substance crystallises out so that pure nitrite becomes separated on fractional crystallisation.

The melting point of the substance and its degrees of dissociation are ascertained and the solubility of the substance at the melting point of ice and the cryohydric point of ice and ammonium chloride are determined.

Numerous attempts have been made to prepare potassium nitrite in a pure state (Gay Lussac, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1816, 27, i, 394; Lang, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1862, 88, 296; Schwarz, *Dingler's J.*, 1869, 191, 397; Persoz, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1878, 157; Muller and Pauly, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1879, 14, 245; Warren, *Chem. News*, 1892, 66, 190, 204; Divers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 1, 85; Milbauer and Jaderic, *Chem. Obzor.*, 1926, 1, 16, 22; Slavina, *Trans. Inst. Pure Chem. Reagents Moscow*, 1930, 10, 21).

One of us made attempts to prepare pure potassium nitrite required for the study of its thermal decomposition (Oza and Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 11, iii, 70) by the double decomposition method with silver nitrite but the method was found to be both tedious and incapable of yielding appreciable amounts because of the low solubility of silver nitrite in water. Moreover, it was found in agreement with Divers (*loc. cit.*) that the nitrite thus prepared was greyish presumably due to contamination with silver chloride. He, therefore, tried the fractional crystallisation method with the commercial nitrite and was successful in separating pure potassium nitrite therefrom. We have now collected the results for presentation. The method, it will be seen from the results, is capable of giving commercial yields.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material.—Merck's pure potassium nitrite worked upon was found to contain on analysis 92.7% potassium nitrite, the rest being potassium nitrate and chloride (trace).

Procedure and Analysis.—A beaker containing a concentrated solution of the commercial substance (sp. gr. 1.615) was cooled in a finely ground intimate mixture of ice and ammonium chloride, the liquors being stirred during the process of cooling. When a sufficient crop of crystals separated, the contents of the beaker were rapidly filtered under the vacuum of the hyvac pump. The mother-liquors adhering to the solid were squeezed out by pressure. The solid was taken out and spread in a dish and kept in a desiccator over sulphuric acid to dry. The mother-liquors were concentrated in an oven maintained at 50-60° and when appropriate concentration was attained they were subjected to the freezing action. Several lots of crystals were separated in this way, and then purity tested with KMnO_4 .

The results of experiments on three different sets are given in Table I. Brackets contain approximate mass of the particular lot whose analytical result (KNO_2 content %) is stated. The results are in serial order from left to right.

TABLE I
Fractional crystallisation of potassium nitrite

Lots marked similarly are mixed together for subsequent crystallisations and results of these given under the sign

Set I.—Crude potassium nitrite (250 g.).

99.4 (8.3)	96.9 (6.8)	97 (6.4)	96.7 (6.3)	97.6 (7.2)	97.6 (7.5)	97.0 (7.3)	97.0 (7.3)	97.3 (7.4)	97.4 (7.5)	97.1 (7.4)	97.4 (7.5)	97.3 (7.4)	96.7 (7.0)	96.5 (6.9)	91.3 (8.2)	91.2 (8.1)	88.2 (7.8)	79.2 (6.7)
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Set II.—Crude potassium nitrite (225 g.).

99.1 (8.2)	98.5 (7.9)	94.3 (7.5)	91.7 (8.1)	94.8 (8.4)	95.3 (8.5)	92.8 (8.2)	93.6 (8.3)	93.8 (8.3)	86.6 (7.5)	86.8 (7.5)	88.3 (7.6)	81.8 (7.7)	83.3 (7.9)	84.5 (8.1)	57.3 (4.3)
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Set III.—Crude potassium nitrite (275 g.).

100 (14.3)	100 (9.3)	100 (6.0)	100 (5.5)	100 (4.6)	98.4 (3.4)	96.7 (2.7)	98.9 (4.7)	99.6 (4.4)	95.8 (2.7)	93.5 (2.8)	98.7 (6.8)	97.1 (6.9)	99.4 (14.7)	98.7 (9.8)	95.5 (6.9)
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° (86.5 g.)

100 (21.2)	95.3 (12.3)	96.3 (11.0)	98.4 (6.6)	88.5	99.8 (3.2)	99.5 (3.3)	97.1 (2.8)	99.8 (1.6)	96.4 (7.1)	98.4 (11.4)	98.7 (13.2)	97.3 (5.6)	98.3 (12.8)	99 (8.7)	98.1 (10.4)	97.4 (6.3)	89.6
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TABLE II

Degrees of dissociation of potassium nitrite

Dilution v (litres)	Depression ° observed	Temp.	M. P. of ice	Cryohydric point of ice and NH ₄ Cl
4	0.845	—	—	—
8	0.43	—	—	—
16	0.22	—	0.86	—
36	0.10	—	0.91	—
72	0.052	—	0.99	—

TABLE III

Solubility of potassium nitrite

Potassium nitrite	Potassium nitrate
I	II
3.45 g. mol/100	3.43 g. mol/100
3.18 g. mol/100	3.29 g. mol/100
3.18 g. mol/100	3.16 g. mol/100
0.1377 g. mol/100	0.1377 g. mol/100
—	(6.736 at 0°)

Working with one and a half pound of potassium nitrite 85 g. of chemically pure nitrite have thus been isolated by us. The analysis of the pure substance is given as:—

0.1130 G. substance gave 0.1144 g. of K_2SO_4 ; giving $K=0.0512$ g.

„ KNO_2 requires $K=0.0518$ g. K (calc.) = 45.8; K (found) = 45.3%.

0.0668 G. substance required 15.7 c.c. of 0.1 N - $KMnO_4$, giving $NO_2=0.0361$ g.

„ KNO_2 requires $NO_2=0.0361$ g. NO_2 (calc.) = 54.1; NO_2 (found) = 54.1%.

The Melting Point of Pure Potassium Nitrite.—Conflicting figures are found in literature for the melting point of pure potassium nitrite; Ostwalds (*Internat. Congress Appl. Chem.*, 1912, 8, ii, 175) gives m.p. 297.5; Von Leugyal (*Naturwiss.*, 1933, 21, 848) gives 419 ± 3 for 96-97% potassium nitrite.

Melting point was determined by taking the powdered substance in a test tube and heating it in an electric furnace. The test tube was placed inside a wider test tube which served as an air jacket and the temperature of melting determined by the help of mercury in a silica thermometer (650°). The liquid state was found to make its appearance first at 410° but the cooling curve of the liquid gave a more accurate m.p. of 407-408°.

Properties of Potassium Nitrite.—The substance separates in small thick prismatic crystals forming a coherent pale yellow sticky mass if not loosened before drying. When ground in a mortar it becomes powdery. It is hygroscopic and does not contain any water of crystallisation.

Degrees of Dissociation of Potassium Nitrite.—Ray and Mukherjee (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 28, 173) determined the degrees of dissociation of pure potassium nitrite by the conductivity method at two different dilutions. We have determined the same by the freezing point method, at dilutions equal to and other than those used by Ray. The results are given in Table II. The last column (α') contains Ray's results and it will be seen that the results agree within the range of expected agreement.

The solubility of potassium nitrite at the melting point of ice and at the cryohydric point of ice and ammonium chloride has been determined. Standard method (Reilly and Rae, "Physico-chemical Methods", p. 415) was used and the amount of potassium nitrite in the liquid phase was determined both by the evaporation and the chemical methods.

Temperature constancy was ensured in the following way. A large vacuum flask, wider in the body than at the mouth, was taken and its bark cork was drilled with five holes, two to contain saturated solutions of potassium nitrite, one to contain a saturated solution of potassium nitrate, a middle one to contain Beckmann thermometer and an outer one to contain a large stirrer. The thermometer indicated a constant temperature for hours together. Potassium nitrate solution froze completely at the cryohydric temperature so that its solubility at this temperature could not be determined. The results obtained are given in Table III. The figures in brackets are from the International Critical Tables at 0° and at -10°.

The results show that a redetermination of the solubility of pure potassium nitrite is necessary. The results in the International tables are due to Ostwald so that presumably his results were obtained with the nitrite of melting point 297.5° (*loc. cit.*).

The system KNO_2 - KNO_3 - H_2O is being studied from the standpoint of the phase rule with a view to ascertaining the exact conditions of temperature and concentration suitable for the isolation of pure potassium nitrite.

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